

Implementing disclosure controls in DataSHIELD demonstrated by the dsSurvival package

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Sofack Ghislain N.

Institute of Medical Biometry and Statistics (IMBI), University Medical Center Freiburg

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Survival analysis

Rationale

- Survival analysis is widely used in medical sciences to analyze the expected duration of time until some event of interest occurs
- The most frequently used model is the cox proportional hazard model (Cox, 1972)
- Performing meta-analysis of survival models requires large amount of data from different sites
 - General Data Protection Regulation
 - Physical size of data

Alternative: DataSHIELD

The DataSHIELD approach

Take “analysis to data” not “data to analysis”

Data Aggregation Ithrough Anonymous Summary-statistics from Harmonized Individual-level EL Databases

Key principles

- Enables federated analysis
- Uses client – server architecture
- Controls disclosure risks

The DataSHIELD approach

Two classes of multi-score analysis

- **Horizontal partitioning**
 - meta-analysis setting
- **Vertical partitioning**
 - record linkage setting

dsSurvival

Privacy preserving fitting of Cox models

- Allow Cox models to be fitted at each study, and then meta analyse the results
- Implementation is restricted to being study-level meta-analysis (SLMA) rather than full likelihood
- Server-side package: [dsSurvival](#)
 - `SurvDS(...)`
 - `coxphSLMADS(...)`
- Client-side package: [dsSurvivalClient](#)
 - `ds.Surv(...)` → assign function
 - `ds.coxphSLMA(...)` → aggregate function

dsSurvival Framework

Privacy preserving fitting of Cox models

AC: Analysis computer
DC: Data computer
DB: Database

Disclosure risks

Survival analysis

- Controlling the risk that the data analyst can deliberately infer to the identity or to one of the key variables being analyzed.
- The results of a survival analysis are likely to be disclosive if:
 - Reveal identifying information, or exact values of variables, including dates, diagnoses, and comorbidities
 - Reveal status of observations

O'Keefe, Christine M., et al. "Confidentialising survival analysis output in a remote data access system." *Journal of Privacy and Confidentiality* 4.1 (2012).

Disclosure risks

Cox proportional hazard models

$$h_i(t) = h_o(t) \exp \left(\sum_{j=1}^p \beta_j x_{ij} \right)$$

Baseline hazard
X
Relative risk of covariates x_i

- Interested in the coefficient estimates β rather than the baseline hazard $h_o(t)$
- Do not release the values of the covariates x_{ij} for each participant
- Do not reveal the hazard function $h_i(t)$ (survival objects) for each participant

Disclosure control

Disclosure checks

- `nfilter.levels`
- `nfilter.tab`
- `nfilter.glm`
- `nfilter.string`
- `nfilter.subset`

Disclosure checks

- Number of parameters in Cox model as a proportion of the sample size
- Default : 20% of sample size
- Prevents model oversaturation

Output presentation

\$study1

	coef	exp(coef)	se(coef)	z	Pr(> z)
D\$age	0.00815	1.008191	0.001248	6.535	6.35e-11 ***
D\$bmi	0.00553	1.005551	0.030356	2.422	0.004245 **
D\$factor(sex)male	0.15224	1.164442	0.065621	0.215	0.000116 **

Signif. Codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1' '1

\$study2

	coef	exp(coef)	se(coef)	z	Pr(> z)
D\$age	0.04067	1.04151	0.00416	9.776	< 2e-16 ***
D\$bmi	-0.62756	0.53389	0.11767	-5.333	9.66e-08 ***
D\$factor(sex)male	-0.66000	0.516850	0.099481	-6.634	3.26e-11 ***

Signif. Codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1' '1

\$study3

	coef	exp(coef)	se(coef)	z	Pr(> z)
D\$age	0.042145	1.043045	0.003086	13.655	< 2e-16 ***
D\$bmi	0.006522	1.005551	0.03359	1.452	0.424513 ***
D\$factor(sex)male	-0.599238	0.549230	0.084305	-7.108	1.18e-12 ***

Signif. Codes: 0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1' '1

Metafor R package

- Meta-analysis of the hazard ratios
- Forest plots of estimates from RE model

<http://www.metafor-project.org>

Summary

- DataSHIELD enables federated analysis and tailored disclosure controls
- dsSurvival is a DataSHIELD package for privacy preserving meta-analysis of survival data distributed across different sites
- A tutorial in bookdown format with code, diagnostics, plots and synthetic data is available here:
- <https://neelsoumya.github.io/dsSurvivalbookdown/>
- All code is available from the following repositories:
- <https://github.com/neelsoumya/dsSurvivalClient/>
- <https://github.com/neelsoumya/dsSurvival/>

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